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DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

The article reveals the importance of modern digital technologies for the development of the economy of Ukraine; the main directions of digitization of the state administration system are analyzed; the problems of digitization of the social sphere and medical care in Ukraine were investigated; global trends of digitalization of ecological development in modern conditions are analyzed; the advantages of the introduction of modern information technologies in the development of an effective energy infrastructure of Ukraine are summarized.

Keywords: digital technologies, digitalization, social sphere, environmental protection, ecological sphere, energy infrastructure.

In today's globalized world, digital technologies play an important role in ensuring sustainable development. They make it possible to optimize resources, increase the efficiency of management and contribute to the introduction of innovations in almost all spheres of human activity. For Ukraine, which is currently facing many challenges, in particular due to the military invasion of the Russian Federation, digital technologies can become a defining element in achieving the goals of sustainable development.

The use of modern IT technologies and digital tools allows enterprises to significantly reduce the cost of production and increase its productivity. This is especially important for small and medium-sized businesses that need support in the modern conditions of Ukraine. E-commerce tools enable businesses to expand sales markets and provide consumers with access to a wider range of goods and services.

Digital technologies stimulate the development of new business models and products, which contributes to economic growth and the creation of new jobs. The

basis of the digital economy is the sector engaged in the production of digital goods and the provision of services related to digital technologies.

In parallel, digital infrastructure is developing, which is becoming more and more accessible and plays an important role in technological innovation. At the same time, there is the emergence of new business models that form network structures based on collective methods of production and consumption. This in a certain way changes classical market relations, requiring the constant creation of new solutions in the field of management and technology development [1].

The introduction of electronic services allows citizens to interact more effectively and efficiently with representatives of state and municipal authorities. This significantly reduces corruption risks and increases the transparency of government processes. The use of large databases and analytics allows the government to make informed decisions and manage resources more efficiently.

It is worth noting that in the process of reforming public administration with the help of information, communication and digital technologies, Ukraine should be guided by the experience of leading countries in the world, which successfully implement digitalization to improve the work of state bodies. Civil servants and officials of state authorities and local self-government should develop digital competences in order to acquire new knowledge, abilities, skills, methods and ways of thinking and vision, as well as other personal qualities in the field of digital and information and communication technologies [2].

The development of digital technologies requires increasing the digital literacy of the population of Ukraine. Investments in digital education contribute to the training of qualified personnel and ensure competitiveness in the labor market.

Digital technologies play a key role in modern health care, providing new opportunities for improving medical services and increasing the efficiency of medical facilities. Among the main areas of application of digital technologies in this area, the following can be distinguished:

- electronic medical records, which allow storing medical information of patients in digital form, which facilitates access to medical history, diagnoses, examination results and treatment;
- telemedicine - patients can receive consultations and medical assistance from doctors without leaving their homes. This is especially important for remote regions and during pandemics;
- mobile health apps that help track health, remind you to take medications, provide information about a healthy lifestyle, etc.;
- with the help of special devices, it is possible to monitor the health status of patients in real time, for example, blood sugar level, heart rate, blood pressure, etc.;
- decision support systems – help doctors in diagnosis and choosing optimal treatment methods, analyzing large volumes of medical data, etc.

The use of digital technologies in health care can improve the quality of medical services, make them more accessible and efficient, and provide a personalized approach to patient treatment. In order to transition to a digital system in the field of social services and provide most social services online, the Government of Ukraine decided to create and implement a Unified Information System of the Social Sector, known as the Unified Social Register. This system stores information about all recipients of social payments, benefits and other types of social support [3].

It should also be noted that popular social platforms facilitate the exchange of information and create conditions for citizen participation in decision-making.

The use of modern digital technologies in urban planning makes it possible to optimize the use of resources, reduce energy consumption and improve the quality of life of the population. Digital sensors and data collection platforms help monitor the state of the

environment and respond to environmental threats in a timely manner.

Among European countries, Ukraine has the highest integrated index of anthropogenic impact on the environment. More effective monitoring of the state and level of environmental pollution can be carried out with the help of digital technologies. Digitization in this area contributes to the coordination and unification of information data at the local, regional, and national levels into a single information database [4].

Innovative digital solutions make it possible to effectively manage the production and consumption of renewable energy sources, which contributes to reducing dependence on traditional energy resources.

Digitalization is the key to the efficient development of energy capacities, the creation, installation and use of energy installations, as well as the formation of new vertical value chains. It allows for a "green" transition faster and cheaper than the development of the oil and gas industry in the 1960s and 1970s. Digitalization ensures balancing of electricity consumption, allowing excess capacity to be returned to the same network.

IT technologies are important for the development of the energy industry and strengthen the related transport and construction industries. Modern IT solutions help companies to automate processes, reduce the number of errors and increase efficiency [5].

Conclusions. Digital technologies are a powerful tool for ensuring the sustainable development of Ukraine. They contribute to economic growth, increase the efficiency of public administration, improve the quality of life of the population and help protect the environment. To fully unlock the potential of digital technologies, it is necessary to make constant investments in digital infrastructure, education and ensuring cyber security. Only thanks to a comprehensive approach, Ukraine will be able to achieve sustainable development in the face of modern challenges.

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